

bioscience

The ISA Commons: experiences from ✓ the field

Susanna-Assunta Sansone, PhD

Principal Investigator, Team Leader,
University of Oxford e-Research Centre,
Oxford, UK

<http://uk.linkedin.com/in/sasansone>

[#biosharing](#)

DataCite

Helping you to find,
access, and **reuse** data

- **Reproducible research**

- annotated research data and methods offer new discovery opportunities and prevent unnecessary repetition of work;
- improved data sharing underpins science of the future;
- but shared data have little or no value if they are not **interpretable** and, consequently, **reusable**

Reproducibility

Nature Genetics **41**, 149 - 155 (2009)

Published online: 28 January 2008 | doi:10.1038/ng.295

Repeatability of published microarray gene expression analyses

See associated Correspondence: [Baggerly, *Nature* **467**, 401 \(September 2010\)](#)

John P A Ioannidis^{1,2,3}, David B Allison⁴, Catherine A Ball⁵, Issa Coulibaly⁴, Xiangqin Cui⁴, Aedín C Culhane^{6,7}, Mario Falchi^{8,9}, Cesare Furlanello¹⁰, Laurence Game¹¹, Giuseppe Jurman¹⁰, Jon Mangion¹¹, Tapan Mehta⁴, Michael Nitzberg⁵, Grier P Page^{4,12}, Enrico Petretto^{11,13} & Vera van Noort¹⁴

Given the complexity of microarray-based gene expression studies, guidelines encourage transparent design and public data availability. Several journals require public data deposition and several public databases exist. However, not all data are publicly available, and even when available, it is unknown whether the published results are reproducible by independent scientists. Here we evaluated the replication of data analyses in 18 articles on microarray-based gene expression profiling published in *Nature Genetics* in 2005–2006. One table or figure from each article was independently evaluated by two teams of analysts. We reproduced two analyses in principle and six partially or with some discrepancies; ten could not be reproduced. The main reason for failure to reproduce was data unavailability, and discrepancies were mostly due to incomplete data annotation or specification of data processing and analysis. Repeatability of published microarray studies is apparently limited. More strict publication rules enforcing public data availability and explicit description of data processing and analysis should be considered.

Ioannidis et al., Repeatability of published microarray gene expression analyses. *Nature Genetics* 41(2), 149-55 (2009) doi:10.1038/ng.295

Reproducibility

Nature Genetics **41**, 149 - 155 (2009)

Published online: 28 January 2008 | doi:10.1038/ng.295

Repeatability of published microarray gene expression analyses

See associated Correspondence: [Baggerly, *Nature* **467**, 401 \(September 2010\)](#)

John P A Ioannidis^{1,2,3}, David B Allison⁴, Catherine A Ball⁵, Issa Coulibaly⁴, Xiangqin Cui⁴, Aedín C Culhane^{6,7}, Mario Falchi^{8,9}, Cesare Furlanello¹⁰, Laurence Game¹¹, Giuseppe Jurman¹⁰, Jon Mangion¹¹, Tapan Mehta⁴, Michael Nitzberg⁵, Grier P Page^{4,12}, Enrico Petretto^{11,13} & Vera van Noort¹⁴

Given the complexity of microarray-based gene expression studies, guidelines encourage transparent design and public data availability. Several journals require public data deposition and several public databases exist. However, not all data are publicly available, and even when available, it is unknown whether the published results are reproducible by independent scientists. Here we evaluated the replication of data analyses in 18 articles on microarray-based gene expression profiling published in *Nature Genetics* in 2005–2006. One table or figure from each article was independently evaluated by two teams of analysts. We reproduced two analyses in principle and six partially or with some

The main reason for failure to reproduce was data unavailability, and discrepancies were mostly due to incomplete data annotation or specification of data processing and analysis. Repeatability of published microarray studies is apparently limited. More strict publication rules enforcing public data availability and explicit description of data processing and analysis should be considered.

Ioannidis et al., Repeatability of published microarray gene expression analyses. *Nature Genetics* 41(2), 149-55 (2009) doi:10.1038/ng.295

Repeatability of published microarray gene expression analyses

See associated Correspondence: [Baggerly, *Nature* **467**, 401 \(September 2010\)](#)

John P A Ioannidis^{1,2,3}, David B Allison⁴, Catherine A Ball⁵, Issa Coulibaly⁴, Xiangqin Cui⁴, Aedín C Culhane^{6,7}, Mario Falchi^{8,9}, Cesare Furlanello¹⁰, Laurence Game¹¹, Giuseppe Jurman¹⁰, Jon Mangion¹¹, Tapan Mehta⁴, Michael Nitzberg⁵, Grier P Page^{4,12}, Enrico Petretto^{11,13} & Vera van Noort¹⁴

Given the complexity of microarray-based gene expression studies, guidelines encourage transparent design and public data availability. Several journals require public data deposition and several public databases exist. However, not all data are publicly

Reproducibility

...n whether the
ent scientists. Here
18 articles on
lished in *Nature*
n each article was
sts. We reproduced
h some
reason for
pancies
ification of
d microarray
les enforcing
processing

Ioannidis et al., Repeatability of published microarray gene expression analyses. *Nature Genetics* **41**(2), 149-55 (2009) doi:10.1038/ng.295

Reproducibility

Michael Stravato for The New York Times

Keith Baggerly, left, and Kevin Coombes, statisticians at M. D. Anderson Cancer Center, found flaws in research on tumors.

By GINA KOLATA
Published: July 7, 2011

When Juliet Jacobs found out she had lung [cancer](#), she was terrified, but realized that her hope lay in getting the best treatment medicine could offer. So she got a second opinion, then a third. In February of 2010, she ended up at [Duke University](#), where she entered a research study whose promise seemed stunning.

But the research at Duke turned out to be wrong. Its gene-based tests proved worthless, and the research behind them was discredited. Ms. Jacobs died a few months after treatment, and her husband and other patients' relatives have retained lawyers.

The episode is a stark illustration of serious problems in a field in which the medical community has placed great hope: using patterns from large groups of genes or other molecules to improve the detection and treatment of cancer. Companies have been formed and products have been introduced that claim to use [genetics](#) in this way, but assertions have turned out to be unfounded. While researchers agree there is great promise in this science, it has yet to yield many reliable methods for diagnosing cancer or identifying the best treatment.

Instead, as patients and their doctors try to make critical decisions about serious illnesses, they may be getting worthless information that is based on bad science. The scientific

Dr. Baggerly and Dr. Coombes found errors almost immediately. Some seemed careless — moving a row or a column over by one in a giant spreadsheet — while others seemed inexplicable. The Duke team shrugged them off as “clerical errors.”

But the research at Duke turned out to be wrong. Its gene-based tests proved worthless, and the research behind them was discredited. Ms. Jacobs died a few months after treatment, and her husband and other patients' relatives have retained lawyers.

The episode is a stark illustration of serious problems in a field in which the medical community has placed great hope: using patterns from large groups of genes or other molecules to improve the detection and treatment of cancer. Companies have been formed and products have been introduced that claim to use [genetics](#) in this way, but assertions have turned out to be unfounded. While researchers agree there is great promise in this science, it has yet to yield many reliable methods for diagnosing cancer or identifying the best treatment.

Instead, as patients and their doctors try to make critical decisions about serious illnesses, they may be getting worthless information that is based on bad science. The scientific

Reproducibility

Michael Stravato for The New York Times

Keith Baggerly, left, and Kevin Coombes, statisticians at M. D. Anderson Cancer Center, found flaws in research on tumors.

By GINA KOLATA
Published: July 7, 2011

When Juliet Jacobs found out she had lung [cancer](#), she was terrified, but realized that her hope lay in getting the best treatment medicine could offer. So she got a second opinion, then a third. In February of 2010, she ended up at [Duke University](#), where she entered a research study whose promise seemed stunning.

But the research at Duke turned out to be wrong. Its gene-based tests proved worthless, and the research behind them was discredited. Ms. Jacobs died a few months after treatment, and her husband and other patients' relatives have retained lawyers.

The episode is a stark illustration of serious problems in a field in which the medical community has placed great hope: using patterns from large groups of genes or other molecules to improve the detection and treatment of cancer. Companies have been formed and products have been introduced that claim to use [genetics](#) in this way, but assertions have turned out to be unfounded. While researchers agree there is great promise in this science, it has not yet yielded reproducible methods for diagnosing cancer or identifying at-

Dr. Baggerly and Dr. Coombes found errors almost immediately. Some seemed careless — moving a row or a column over by one in a giant spreadsheet — while others seemed inexplicable. The Duke team shrugged them off as “clerical errors.”

DataCite

Helping you to find,
access, and **reuse** data

NO to 'data blobs'

YES to verifiable, complete
and structured information

Structured description of datasets

- Capture all salient features of the experimental workflow
- Make annotation explicit and discoverable
- Structure the descriptions for consistency, tracking
 - independent variables
 - dependent variables using
 - cross reference and resolvable identifiers

Not too much, not too little, just 'right'

- We must strike a balance between
 - depth and breadth of information; and
 - sufficient information required to reuse the data

	liver	kidney	blood serum plasma		urine
protein expression profiling by mass spectrometry	✓	✓	✓		✓
transcription profiling by dna microarray	✓	✓	✓	✓	
metabolite profiling by mass spectrometry	✓	✓	✓		✓
metabolite profiling by nmr spectroscopy	✓	✓	✓		✓
histology	✓	✓			
clinical chemistry			✓	✓	✓
hematology			✓	✓	

**Example of experiments by
InnoMed PredTox**
a FP6 public-private consortium

Different community, different norms and standards, e.g.:

formats

allow data to flow from one system to another

terminologies

use the same word and refer to the same 'thing'

guidelines

report the same core, essential information

Challenges: lack of coordination, fragmentation and uneven coverage

Growing number of reporting standards

A CATALOGUE OF STANDARDS

You can **sort** columns and **browse** the reporting guidelines content, or you can view [all the standards](#), or [terminological artifacts](#) or [exchange formats](#) only; or go back to the [catalogue main page](#).

ACRONYM	FULL NAME	TYPE▲	DOMAIN	VERSION	PUBLICATION	CONTACT
BioPAX	Biological Pathway Exchange	exchange format	biological pathway	Level 3	Demir et al; Nat Biotech; 2010	BioPAX community
CellML	Cell Markup Language	exchange format	cell modelling	v 1.1	Cuellar et al; Simulation; 2003	CellML community
SBML	System Biology Markup Language	exchange format	computational modelling (biochemical reaction networks)	level 3, v 1 core	Hucka et al; Bioinformatics; 2003	SBML community
FuGE	Functional Genomics Experiment Markup Language	exchange format	experimental description	v 1.0	Jones et al; Nature Biotech; 2007	FuGE working group
ISA-Tab	Investigation/Study/Assay Tabular	exchange format	experimental description	v 1.0	Rocca-Serra et al; Bioinformatics; 2010	ISA working group
MINiML	MIAME Notation in Markup Language	exchange format	experimental description (functional genomics)	v 1.0		GEO
SOFT	Simple Omnibus Format in Text	exchange format	experimental description (functional genomics)	not versioned		GEO
GCDML	Genomic Contextual Data Markup Language	exchange format	experimental description (genomics)	v 2.0.0 beta	Kottmann et al; OMICS; 2008	GSC
MAGE-Tab	MicroArray Gene Expression Tabular	exchange format	experimental description (transcriptomics)	v 1.0	Rayner et al; BMC Bioinformatics; 2006	FGED Society
GelML	Gel Electrophoresis Markup Language	exchange format	gel electroph			
mzML	mz Markup Language	exchange format	mass spectro (proteomics)			
MIABE	Minimum Information About a Bioactive Entity	reporting guideline	bioactive enti			
MIPFE	Minimal Information for Protein Functional Evaluation	reporting guideline	biochemistry			
BioCoreDB	Core Attributes of Biological Databases	reporting guideline	biological dat			
GIATE	Guidelines for Information About Therapy Experiments	reporting guideline	cancer therap experiments			
MIRIAM	Minimal Information Required In the Annotation of biochemical Models	reporting guideline	computation: modeling			

A **catalogue** to map the landscape of standards and the systems implementing them:
Over 400 bio-standards
 (public and in curation)

Field*, Sansone* et al., Omics data sharing. **Science** 326, 234-36 (2009) doi:0.1126/science.1180598

A CATALOGUE OF STANDARDS

You can **sort** columns and **browse** the reporting guidelines content, or you can view [all the standards](#), or [terminological artifacts](#) or [exchange formats](#) only; or go back to the [catalogue main page](#).

ACRONYM	FULL NAME	TYPE▲	DOMAIN	VERSION	PUBLICATION	CONTACT
BioPAX	Biological Pathway Exchange	exchange	biological pathway	Level 3	Demir et al; Nat	BioPAX community

POLICIES

A catalogue of data preservation, management and sharing policies from international funding agencies and regulators.

STANDARDS

A catalogue of reporting standards (minimum reporting guidelines, exchange formats and terminologies) and organizations that develop these.

DATABASES

A catalogue of databases, described according to the BioDBcore guidelines, along with the standards used within them; compiled in collaboration with 2012 NAR Database.

GelML	Gel Electrophoresis Markup Language	exchange format	gel electroph
mzML	mz Markup Language	exchange format	mass spectro (proteomics)
MIABE	Minimum Information About a Bioactive Entity	reporting guideline	bioactive enti
MIPFE	Minimal Information for Protein Functional Evaluation	reporting guideline	biochemistry
BioCoreDB	Core Attributes of Biological Databases	reporting guideline	biological dat
GIATE	Guidelines for Information About Therapy Experiments	reporting guideline	cancer therap experiments
MIRIAM	Minimal Information Required In the Annotation of biochemical Models	reporting guideline	computation: modeling

A **catalogue** to map the landscape of standards and the systems implementing them:
Over 400 bio-standards (public and in curation)

Field*, Sansone* et al., Omics data sharing. *Science* 326, 234-36 (2009) doi:0.1126/science.1180598

Bioscience is not one domain...

- Bioscience is **interdisciplinary** and **integrative** in character
 - need to deal with **new** and **existing** datasets
 - deal with a **variety** of data types

Source of the figure: EBI website

Is it possible to achieve a **common, structured representation** of diverse bioscience experiments that:

- transcends individual bioscience domains, but also
- follows the appropriate community norms and standards?

A growing **ecosystem of over 30 public and internal resources** using the **ISA metadata tracking framework** to facilitate **standards-compliant** collection, curation, management and reuse of investigations in an increasingly diverse set of life science domains, including:

- environmental health
- environmental genomics
- metabolomics
- metagenomics
- nanotechnology
- proteomics,
- stem cell discovery
- system biology
- transcriptomics
- toxicogenomics
- also by communities working to build a library of cellular signatures

We aim to achieve a common representation of experimental content that transcends individual bioscience domains

A growing **ecosystem of over 30 public and internal resources** using the **ISA metadata tracking framework** to facilitate **standards-compliant** collection, curation, management and reuse of investigations in an increasingly diverse set of life science domains, including:

- environmental health
- environmental genomics
- metabolomics
- metagenomics
- nanotechnology
- proteomics
- stem cell discovery
- system biology
- transcriptomics
- toxicogenomics
- also by communities working to build a library of cellular signatures

Some of the public groups/resources:

Some of the internal projects:

A growing **ecosystem of over 30 public and internal resources** using the **ISA metadata tracking framework** to facilitate **standards-compliant** collection, curation, management and reuse of investigations in an increasingly diverse set of life science domains, including:

- environmental health
- environmental genomics
- metabolomics
- metagenomics
- nanotechnology
- proteomics
- stem cell discovery
- system biology
- transcriptomics
- toxicogenomics
- also by communities working to build a library of cellular signatures

doi>

Some of the public groups/resources:

Some of the internal projects:

investigation

high level concept to link related studies

study

the central unit, containing information on the subject under study, its characteristics and any treatments applied.

*a study has associated **assays***

assay

test performed either on material taken from the subject or on the whole initial subject, which produce qualitative or quantitative measurements (data)

Metadata tracking framework, designed to support the use of several **standards checklists, terminologies** conversions to (a growing number of) other metadata **formats**, used by public repositories, e.g.

MAGE-Tab

Pride-xml

SRA-xml

SOFT

Currently finalizing conversion to RDF to explore the growing Linked Data universe, in collaboration with the W3C HCLSIG)

empowering researchers to use standards

Feb 2012

Sansone SA, Rocca-Serra P, Field D, Maguire E, Taylor C, Hofmann O, Fang H, Neumann S, Tong W, Amaral-Zettler L, Begley K, Booth T, Bougueleret L, Burns G, Chapman B, Clark T, Coleman LA, Copeland J, Das S, de Daruvar A, de Matos P, Dix I, Edmunds S, Evelo C, Forster M, Gaudet P, Gilbert J, Goble C, Griffin J, Jacob D, Kleinjans J, Harland L, Haug K, Hermjakob H, Sui S, Laederach A, Liang S, Marshall S, Merrill E, McGrath A, Reilly D, Roux M, Shamu C, Shang C, Steinbeck C, Trefethen A, Williams-Jones B, Wolstencroft K, Xenarios J, Hide W.

www.isacommons.org

Community involvement and uptake

Core developments

Publications

2007 2008 2009 2010 2011 2012

Development timeline